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MODIFICATIONS OF VOWELS IN CONNECTED SPEECH

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ANNOTATION

This article gives information about in connected speech vowels can change their quality under the influence of other sounds.

Key words: Quantitative, qualitative, rhythm, stress, unstressed, vowel elision, reduction.

Learn more about the five main types of connected speech. Catenation (linking words), Intrusion (adding an extra sound), Elision (deleting a sound),

Assimilation (joining sounds to make a new sound). Geminates (twin sounds) To make a more convenient transition from one articulation to another the speech organs adjust themselves, they display a certain "economy" of effort > the phenomenon of adaptation. The modifications of phonemes are conditioned : by the complementary distribution of the phonemes: e.g., the fully back /u:/ > backadvanced as in tune [tju:n], mute [mju:t]; by the contextual variations at the junction of words: alveolar /n/ > dental as in: in the [ɪn ðɒ]; by the style of speech –official or rapid colloquial: [ɪslait ɪpreʃɪ] > [ɪslai ɪpreʃɪ]. Modifications of Consonants : assimilation, accommodation, elision Assimilation is the chief factor under the influence of which the principal allophones of the phonemes are modified into subsidiary ones. Types of assimilation: affecting the direction: - progressive – dogs [dɒgz], price [praɪs]; - regressive – mutton [mʌtn]; - double or reciprocal - twice [twais] ; Modifications of Vowels: reduction, elision Reduction is a historical process of weakening, shortening and disappearance of vowel sounds in unstressed positions. Reduction reflects connection with: the process of lexical and grammatical changes: combine (n) ['kɒmbain] – combine (v) [k əm'bain]; active ['æktɪv] – activity [ə k'tɪvɪtɪ] Phoneme Alternations. The Concept of Neutralization Panov M.V. (The MPhS): The relation of this or that speech sound to this or that phoneme is stated not by their articulatory and acoustic similarity but by the position of sounds in a morpheme. Compare: но[ɾ]а – но[к] – но[ш]ка –но[ж]енька – we deal with the so called sound alternation which may be found in similar or the same morphemes.

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